

PERFORMANCE-BASED VIDEO LESSONS IN COOKERY FOR GRADE 10 LEARNERS

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Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 Learners. It was conducted at Teresa National High School during Academic Year 2022-2023 with Grade 10 Junior High School students taking up TLE 10 Cookery. The researcher pushed through this study to provide an instructional video material that will equip the learners with the necessary knowledge and skills particularly in cookery so that they can improve their performance skills in the subject. Descriptive developmental method was used to describe and evaluate the developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 Learners. Meanwhile, qualitative discussion was used that answered how the Performance-Based Learning Video Lessons was developed. Mean was used to evaluate the developed performance-based learning video lessons as instructional materials in teaching TLE Cookery 10 with respect to content quality, instructional quality and technical quality. Based on the findings, the performance-based video lessons in cookery for Grade 10 learners were accepted based on the criteria used. The content quality, instructional quality and technical quality of the developed performance-based video lessons are very satisfactory based on the evaluation of the experts. In addition, it was concluded that the developed video materials are potential instructional materials that would help the learners understand clearly the lessons in TLE.

Keywords: *video lessons, cookery, performance-based, grade 10*

Introduction

With the emergence of 21st-century education, everyone has concentrated on the convenience of using technology resources, primarily videos as a medium of instructions where teachers and learners can access easily. In fact, it's clear from witnessing lessons in public schools that technology has taken over not only the classroom's instruction and learning activities, but also the learning environment. The availability of technological resources in the classroom is one of the criteria for judging the quality of instruction, and the extent to which students use technological tools is a measure of how well the instructor has incorporated technology using video as a medium of instruction in teaching that will be a great help for the learners to easily understand the lessons.

Being an educator, the researcher has been observing that videos are considered as one of the reasons that help to increase student engagement in their lessons which in turn helps the learners to boost achievement. The use of videos in the lessons helps stimulates the cognitive processes of thinking, reasoning, problem solving, decision making and creating that serve as guide in their lessons on how to do that certain activity.

Technology and Livelihood Education subject is a performance-based subject based on observation; some learners cannot perform well in this particular subject most specifically in their performance task. Some cannot easily follow and understand the module or the teacher instruction on how to do the performance task so the researcher considered other ways on how to help the learners to do their performance activity and that is developing a performance-based learning video lessons that will help the learners to easily follow and guide them in doing performance tasks.

Based on the report of the office of school of Teresa National High School, the performance of the Grade 10 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education for the past years, TLE did not meet the 75% mastery level, which means it is a great challenge for the teacher on how to increase the result of the Learning Outcome Assessment of the school in Grade 10 TLE. Upon the researcher's observation, one of the reasons why 75% mastery level was not met is the low result of the performance task. The researcher thought of the different learning strategies that cater all kinds of learners for them to perform and understand easily the tasks.

This study illustrated the importance of technology and the impact on how to use effectively the computers and video as instructional materials to improve academic performance of the learners. Videos can help address the problems of some learners in terms of academic performance. These serve as the learners' guide, and give the opportunity to the learners to learn at their own pace.

Through this study, the researcher hoped that students would be motivated to learn and perform well in different learning areas. They would be able to easily follow and understand the teachers' instructions with the help and guide of the performance-based learning video lessons. The use of videos is one of the best and highly effective educational tools that can be used to motivate and improve student performance.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to develop performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners at Teresa National High School during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions.

1. How are performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners developed?

2. How do the experts evaluate the developed performance-based video lessons in Cookery with respect to:
 - 2.1. content quality;
 - 2.2. instructional quality;
 - 2.3. technical quality; and
 - 2.4. accuracy?
3. What are the comments and suggestions of the experts on the developed performance-based video lessons in Cookery with respect to the above-mentioned criteria?

Literature Review

According to Brame (2016), videos may provide a significant means to improve student learning and enhance student engagement in Biology courses. That somehow related to researchers' study that proves video has a great help in improving learning which has positively affected student achievement and motivation which can lead the learners to do or perform well.

Furthermore, Chick et al. (2020), stated that instructional media plays a significant role in affecting the processes of learning. Many innovative teaching tools have been developed and used over years to offer excellence in teaching in schools; video instructional media is one of them. It provides for the ability to easily present static and moving materials; it also afford the option of adding animation for clarity. Used prudently, the media has the potential of making a positive influence on student performance.

A video-viewing procedure related to a course in an Environmental Control Systems was developed by the author in a classroom situation at an undergraduate level. The purpose of this study was to determine whether student performance at an undergraduate level is affected by showing related video clips in a classroom situation, supplemented by presentation of course materials in a traditional format.

In addition, Jeremias et al. (2022), stated that the development and evaluation of the video lessons focused on the developmental process of video lessons designed by the researcher. Findings revealed that the video lessons are effective on all corners of the classroom in which educators can use it to create time and space for active learning. This suggest that the teaching and learning will come up to greater heights of performance on the part of the students and contentment on the part of the teachers.

According to Insorio et al. (2022), modular distance learning is a new learning delivery modality implemented by most public schools in the Philippines. Hence, Mathematics concepts were hard to understand and not explained well in the module. To address the problem, the teacher made video lessons and uploaded them to the YouTube channel Direct to the Point by DM as interventions. A YouTube channel as an avenue to upload educational videos has been used before the pandemic.

Based on the study of Zhu et al. (2022), video is a key integral part of online education, largely influences student learning experiences. Though many guidelines on designing educational videos have been reported, the quantitative data showing the impacts of video length on students' academic performance in a credit-bearing course is limited, particularly for an online-flipped college engineering course.

Furthermore, Ali (2019) stated that there is a great impact of watching videos on the academic performance of the learners. He revealed that watching educational videos affected the academic activities and performance of the respondents positively. Most of the respondents used mobile phones and laptops to watch videos. The study further confirmed that most of the respondents preferred short length videos and animated educational videos.

Thus, the videos create a more engaging experience in a learner, which turn helps boost achievement of the students which is very helpful for students to perform well in the class just like what the researcher wants in conducting this study to help the learners in increasing their performance in TLE subjects.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive and developmental methods of research. Descriptive research involves gathering of data that describe events and then organizes, tabulates, depicts, and describes the data collection. In addition, descriptive research is a process of collecting data, analyzing, classifying and tabulating data about prevailing situations, practices, beliefs, processes, trends and cause effect relationships and then provides adequate and precise interpretation about such data with or without aid of tools (Gorard, 2013).

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. To evaluate the instructional videos in Cookery, an adopted questionnaire checklist from LRMDs was used to determine how the respondents evaluated the materials in terms of content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality.

The researcher also utilized developmental research since the study developed an instructional video material, wherein developmental research is a process of translating the design specification into physical form. In other words, developmental method is the systematic study of putting into design, developing and careful evaluation of instructional programs, processes and products that must meet the standard or criteria.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 10 TLE teachers who are teaching TLE from Teresa National High School who were selected through purposive sampling. This study utilized descriptive design of research using an adapted standardized questionnaire checklist from LRMDS to gather the important data and information for the study.

Instrument

To gather reliable data in the conduct of the study, the researcher used the adopted questionnaire from the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) of DepEd. The developed performance-based video lesson was evaluated by the experts based on the following criteria, content quality, instructional quality and technical quality using a 4-point Likert scale in describing the criteria in assessing the learning materials.

Procedure

The evaluation tool for non-print materials from the Department of Education was adopted by the researcher. It was utilized as a questionnaire checklist with the 4-point Likert scale. The questionnaire checklist was face validated by the 10 experts from TLE Department of Teresa National High School base on the given scale.

Data gathered from the questionnaire checklist was used to determine the level of acceptability of the Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 Learners as evaluated by TLE teachers in terms of content quality, instructional quality, technical quality and accuracy.

The result of the evaluated learning materials determined the validity of the video as a tool in teaching Cookery 10. The respondents' comments and suggestions were also requested as this plays an important role in determining which area of the learning material needs to be improved.

After the respondents answered the questionnaire checklist, the researcher consolidated and analyze the data for interpretation, and based on the result, the researcher came up with conclusions and recommendations of the study.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Development of Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 Learners

The data needed in the development of performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners, were gathered from the following sources, DepEd Curriculum Guide for Cookery 10, and other related instructional materials. The researcher also took advantage of the use of internet as one of the main sources of data related to the study.

The performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners covered and based on the least mastered skills result for the School Year 2021-2022 and based on the result, third and fourth quarters have the least result among the four quarters. This material will actively engage learners and provide enough activities to increase their knowledge and performed well in their performance-based task. This will also prove them opportunity to reflect on their learning presents and perform their task clearly. The output comprised of 2 videos, the selected topics are the ones included in the third and fourth quarters listed in the most essential learning competencies provided by the DepEd which are the least mastered skills in Cookery 10. Each video demonstrates the understanding of the basic concepts and underlying theories in preparing a dish for the third quarter. The competency needed is to determine the poultry cuts in accordance with prescribed dish while the fourth quarter competency is to identify the appropriate cooking methods of meat, specifically how to identify the doneness of meat.

To accentuate the organization of content, the researcher created her own video on how to cut a whole poultry and identify its different cuts, and showed how to identify the different doneness of meat. The researcher believed that video lessons for learners are one of the best ways to help the learners to do their performance task and help them to perform well. They can also help motivate the students to create a distinctive performance in their learning experience and open the opportunity for teachers to use video as an instructional material that will be a great help in imparting knowledge.

The proponent of the output was optimistic and determined to bring out the best in the learners and provide challenging, fulfilling and rewarding hours and experience while teaching Cookery 10.

The development of performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners was validated with respect to content quality, instructional quality and technical quality using the adopted questionnaire checklist from LRMDS.

Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery

The results show that the content quality of the developed video lessons are consistent with topics, accurate, and up to date, and promote critical thinking positive values that support formative growth that delivered correct results and fulfilled the intended functions properly as evaluated by the experts. Furthermore, the findings showed the potential to improve learning experiences of its user.

Table 1. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery with Respect to Content Quality*

	<i>Content Quality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Content is consistent with topics/skills found in DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.	Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives	3.70	Very Satisfactory
3.	Content is accurate	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4.	Content is up to date	4.00	Very Satisfactory
5.	Content is logically developed and organized	3.80	Very Satisfactory
6.	Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.80	Very Satisfactory
7.	Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
8.	Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.90	Very Satisfactory
9.	Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level	4.00	Very Satisfactory
10.	Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.92	Very Satisfactory

The findings imply that the performance-based video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners contain clear content that enables the learner to understand the different topics which were considered as least mastered skills. Moreover, the said video lessons are suitable to the student's level of learning abilities which can contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives of each topic.

Findings support the study of De Leon (2013) which stated that, to assess the suitability of the created competency-based learning activities for teaching Elementary Algebra, the content of the instructional materials is appropriate for the learner's level of understanding are specific and easy.

Table 2. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery with Respect to Instructional Quality*

	<i>Instructional Quality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Purpose of the material is well defined.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.	Material achieves its defined purpose.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
3.	Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4.	Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
5.	Graphics/colors/sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.60	Very Satisfactory
6.	Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
7.	Material is effectively stimulating creativity of target user.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
8.	Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.80	Very Satisfactory
9.	Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
10.	Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.94	Very Satisfactory

The findings show that the developed video lessons in Cookery for Grade 10 learners are well defined, achieve its purpose, have objectives that are clearly stated and instruction that is integrated with target user's experience meaning that the video lessons are appropriate and with clear instructions that can stimulate the creativity of a target user.

It could imply that developers should maintain consistency and standardization in the instructional quality. This includes using appropriate material. Additional presentation must also be engaging, interesting and understandable and leveraging their potential to engage learners visually and promote users' level of understanding.

The results are supported by the findings of Cadiz (2015) that instructional design is an organized procedure for developing instruction that includes all afore-cited processes, that is based on the premise that learning should not occur in a haphazard manner but should be developed in orderly processes and has outcomes that can be measured.

The result in table 3 explains that the video lessons in Cookery are user friendly since the target user navigate freely the material and can run using minimum system requirements and can be used easily and independently, the display text, design and visuals are clear which makes the topics easy to understand.

The findings reveal that the experts agreed on the importance of technical quality on the developed video lessons in teaching Cookery. Technical quality in video lessons is important because it makes sure everything looks and sounds good.

Clear audio and video help students understand better and stay interested to the lessons. Good technical quality of video lessons makes learning much easier, plus it helps students easily access the lessons which is the main goal of the material.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery with Respect to Technical Quality

	Technical Quality	Mean	VI
1.	Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.70	Very Satisfactory
2.	Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.70	Very Satisfactory
3.	There is complete synchronization of audio with visuals, if any.	3.70	Very Satisfactory
4.	Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.90	Very Satisfactory
5.	Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
6.	Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.90	Very Satisfactory
7.	Visual sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
8.	Visuals provide accurate presentation of the concept discussed.	3.90	Very Satisfactory
9.	The user support materials (if any) are effective.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
10.	The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
11.	The material can easily and independently be used.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
12.	The material will run using minimum system requirements.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
13.	The program is free from technical problems	3.80	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.89	Very Satisfactory

As Aroonsrimarakot et al. (2023), stated that the identified factors for the technical concern were distraction due to noise and poor learning environment at home, teacher's competency due to technical, poor teaching skills, unstructured content or no follow-up and technological constraint affecting the quality of audio/video uploaded connectivity, technical issue or data limit. Students also suggested strategies to overcome online learning challenges such as improvement in evaluation, connectivity, interactivity, content and accessing materials.

Table 4. Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery with Respect to Accuracy

	Accuracy	Mean	VI
1.	Conceptual Errors	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.	Factual Errors	4.00	Very Satisfactory
3.	Grammatical and /or typographical errors.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4.	Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visual, etc.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	4.00	Very Satisfactory

It could be gleaned from the table that all items got the mean of 4.00, interpreted verbally as very satisfactory. Which means that the overall mean is 4.00 and interpreted also as very satisfactory. It simply implies that based on the expert's evaluation that the instructional materials are free from all errors and very satisfactory and recommended to use as instructional materials that will be a great help for the students.

Findings support the study of Rahmawati et al. (2021) that accurate contents help learners avoid misinformation and misconceptions of content in learning materials.

Comments and Suggestions of the Experts on the Developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery

The developed Performance-Based Video Lessons in Cookery show a very positive response from the experts. Experts were very impressed. They also emphasized that the instructional videos are very interactive, child friendly and easy to access.

The consistency between content and learning competencies are present, it also reflects the latest trend and practices of teaching and also the content is relevant to learners' need and interest, and also the materials provide accurate and credible information that meet the educational needs of the learners, as well have clear learning objectives and interactive content as stated by the experts.

Furthermore with regard to the comments about the instructional quality, the video appears engaging and interactive to user, another expert emphasized that the material achieves specific learning goals such as mastery of new skill and stated also that the materials provide a clear explanation and step by step procedure and seems suitable for use with basic understanding of the subject matter and lastly one expert commented that the materials are accessible to accommodate all types of learners and the instructional design of the material is well throughout incorporating a variety of instructional strategies.

On the other hand, the comments and suggestions of the experts with regard to the technical quality states that the material exhibits high quality and clear audio, one expert says that it has a smooth transition and well-paced delivery of lessons, and the audio of the material is clear, and also the visual and audio element are presented and lastly one comment by the experts is the material is compatible with variety of devices, allowing learners to access easily the instructional materials.

Moreover, the feedback received from the experts regarding the video lessons as instructional materials was predominantly positive. The experts acknowledged the instructional materials potential to improve the performance of the students in this subject. Furthermore, experts highlighted that the instructional materials was intuitive and easy to use. In general, the material is a great help to the learners to improve their learning and performance skills which help to improve the quality of education.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The developed performance-based video materials are potential instructional materials that would help the learners understand the lessons in TLE.

The developed video lessons in TLE were found to help in developing the students' skills in Cookery.

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